

EXCEL SPREADSHEET FOR ASSESSING CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON STREAMFLOW USING TEMEZ HYDROLOGICAL MODEL – INSTRUCTIONS

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This document describes a workbook of Microsoft Excel designed to be used in a post-graduate civil engineering master's degree to assess the long-term impact of climate change on streamflow in a watershed using the lumped hydrological Temez model. The spreadsheet contains 17 worksheets with the different stages of the process, as described below.

Within the spreadsheet, the cells are colour-coded:

Yellow	Data to be entered by the user
Green	Calculated variable
Pink	Iteration variable
Blue	Intermediate results
Orange	Performance results
Purple	Auxiliary optimization variables

Worksheet 0. – ETP	3
Worksheet 1.1. – Initial Model	3
Worksheet 1.2. – Initial Performance	3
Worksheet 2.1. – Calibrated model	3
Worksheet 2.2. – Performance calibrated model	4
Worksheet 3. – Water balance	4
Worksheet 4.1. - Model_Precipitation_CFSR	4
Worksheet 4.2. – Initial Performance P_CFSR	4
Worksheet 4.3. – Calibrated Model P_CFSR	5
Worksheet 4.4. – Performance Calibr P_CFSR	5
Worksheet 5.1. – Model_Thorntwaite	5
Worksheet 5.2. – Performance_Thorntwaite	6
Worksheet 6. – Sensitivity Analysis	6
Worksheet 7.1. – Climate Change Data	6

Worksheet 7.2. – ETP Climate Change	6
Worksheet 7.3. – Climate Change Historic	7
Worksheet 7.4. – Climate Change RCP4.5	7
Worksheet 7.5. – Climate Change RCP8.5	7
Worksheet 7.6. – Climate Change Water balance	7

Worksheet 0. – ETP

To facilitate the use of the workbook, this worksheet evaluates the Potential Evapotranspiration (ETP) providing the values for Hargreaves and Thornthwaite formulae. Notwithstanding, the Hargreaves method is the one used in this workbook but 5.1 and 5.2. worksheets.

The input data are date, maximum and minimum daily temperature, and latitude correction coefficients.

Finally, a comparative graphic of values obtained with the two methods is shown.

Worksheet 1.1. – Initial Model

This worksheet provides initial values of monthly streamflow with a non-calibrating model. The parameters of the Témez model are set randomly.

The input data are the watershed area, the monthly precipitation in the period considered, the observed streamflow in gauge station and initial values of parameters of the Témez model (α , H_{max} , I_{max} and C) and initial values (H_0 and Q_0). Calibration and validation periods are also set.

Worksheet 1.2. – Initial Performance

This worksheet assesses the goodness-of-fit in two different periods in previous non-calibrated model according to Moriasi et al. (2007) criteria (NSE, PBIAS, RSR, and R^2).

Worksheet 2.1. – Calibrated model

This worksheet provides values of monthly streamflow with a calibrated model. The Excel optimization function Solver is used: Cells $\$C\2 , $\$C\3 , $\$C\4 y $\$C\5 are changed (subject to the range in $\$D\$2:\$E\5) to obtain the minimum value ($\$S\4) of the sum of differences between observed and simulated streamflow squared.

SOLVER	
Set cell:	$\$S\4
To value:	Minimum
By changing cells:	$\$C\$2:\$C\5
Subject to the constraints:	$\$C\$2 \leq \$E\2
	$\$C\$2 \geq \$D\2

	\$CS\$3<=\$E\$3
	\$CS\$3>=\$D\$3
	\$CS\$4<=\$E\$4
	\$CS\$4>=\$D\$4
	\$CS\$5<=\$E\$5
	\$CS\$5>=\$D\$5

Worksheet 2.2. – Performance calibrated model

This worksheet assesses the goodness-of-fit in calibration and validation periods of calibrated model in worksheet 2.1 according to Moriasi et al. (2007) criteria (NSE, PBIAS, RSR, and R²).

Worksheet 3. – Water balance

This worksheet provides the following graphics and their values:

- Average monthly hydrograph, where observed versus simulated values are compared.
- Comparison between observed, simulated-calibrated and simulated-non calibrated streamflow values, throughout the studied period.

Worksheet 4.1. - Model_Precipitation_CFSR

This worksheet assesses the monthly streamflow values using CFSR-Precipitation data. The previous-performance validated parameters are used.

Users enter CFSR-daily precipitation and data are aggregated on a monthly basis to compare to monthly observed streamflow.

Worksheet 4.2. – Initial Performance P_CFSR

This worksheet assesses the goodness-of-fit in calibration and validation periods of previous model (4.1.) according to Moriasi et al. (2007) criteria (NSE, PBIAS, RSR, and R²).

Worksheet 4.3. – Calibrated Model P_CFSR

This worksheet provides the values of monthly streamflow with a calibrated model with precipitation from CFSR. The Excel optimization function Solver is used: Cells \$C\$2, \$C\$3, \$C\$4 y \$C\$5 are changed (subject to the range in \$D\$2:\$E\$5) to obtain the minimum value (\$S\$4) of the sum of differences between observed and simulated streamflow squared.

SOLVER	
Set cell:	\$S\$4
To value:	Minimum
By changing cells:	\$C\$2:\$C\$5
Subject to the constraints:	\$C\$2<=\$E\$2
	\$C\$2>=\$D\$2
	\$C\$3<=\$E\$3
	\$C\$3>=\$D\$3
	\$C\$4<=\$E\$4
	\$C\$4>=\$D\$4
	\$C\$5<=\$E\$5
	\$C\$5>=\$D\$5

Worksheet 4.4. – Performance Calibr P_CFSR

This worksheet assesses the goodness-of-fit in calibration and validation periods of calibrated model with precipitation from CFSR in worksheet 4.1 according to Moriasi et al. (2007) criteria (NSE, PBIAS, RSR, and R²).

It also provides the following graphics:

- Comparison between observed and CFSR precipitation data.
- Comparison between observed Precipitation and CFSR-Precipitation simulated streamflow and observed streamflow.

Worksheet 5.1. – Model_Thorntwaite

This worksheet assesses the monthly streamflow values using Thorntwaite ETP data obtained in Worksheet 0.

The previous-performance validated parameters in Worksheet 2.1. are used.

Worksheet 5.2. – Performance_Thorntwaite

This worksheet assesses the goodness-of-fit in calibration and validation periods of previous model (5.1.) with Thorntwaite ETP data according to Moriasi et al. (2007) criteria (NSE, PBIAS, RSR, and R²).

Worksheet 6. – Sensitivity Analysis

A sensitivity analysis of the Témez model parameters is performed in order to test the influence of each one in the performance of the model using the relative error volume (REV) statistic defined by:

$$REV = \frac{M_t - O_t}{O_t} \cdot 100$$

where M_t is the total simulated runoff, and O_t is the total observed runoff.

Users vary the value of one parameter of the Témez model in column C2:C7 within the range of the matrix \$D\$2:\$E\$5, remaining invariable the rest of parameters. The REV value in each iteration will be found in cell \$S\$3\$. Results should be written in column T, depending on the parameter. Finally, the graphics for all the parameters are drawn with the Parameter-REV pairs obtained.

Worksheet 7.1. – Climate Change Data

Daily climate change data (precipitation and maximum and minimum temperatures) for the historic and projection periods are required to enter.

Rows \$B\$C\$6:\$B\$F\$6 and \$B\$C\$8:\$B\$F\$8 provide the percentage of variation in average Precipitation and maximum, minimum and mean temperature of historic period versus climate change scenarios.

Worksheet 7.2. – ETP Climate Change

This worksheet provides monthly ETP for Hargreaves formula according to climate change projection scenarios. User is required to enter daily maximum and minimum precipitations for the periods studied.

Worksheet 7.3. – Climate Change Historic

This worksheet provides monthly streamflow values for the historic period studied with previously calibrated parameters in worksheet 2.1.

Worksheet 7.4. – Climate Change RCP4.5

This worksheet provides monthly streamflow values for the RCP4.5 period with previously calibrated parameters in worksheet 2.1.

Worksheet 7.5. – Climate Change RCP8.5

This worksheet provides monthly streamflow values for the RCP8.5 period with previously calibrated parameters in worksheet 2.1.

Worksheet 7.6. – Climate Change Water balance

This worksheet provides the following graphic and their values:

- Comparison between RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 streamflow values, throughout the studied period.